

Geometry and correlation of the nappe stack in the Ibero-Armorican arc across the Bay of Biscay: a joint French-Spanish project

Part 1: the data

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Since its early recognition and widespread acceptance following the birth of plate tectonics, the Ibero-Armorican arc has been acknowledged as a first-order structure of the Variscan belt. Palaeomagnetic and structural data indicate that the arc dates from the latest Carboniferous (Stephanian, c.a. 305-295 Ma) and that it bends structures that were previously essentially linear. The latter include a huge nappe stack that was built during the early phases of the Variscan orogeny.

Our primary aim was to establish the geometry of the nappe stack on both sides of the Bay of Biscay, and therefore to unify the terminology used by both teams when describing it (see figure). Field excursions have been made in common for checking whether or not both lithologies and structures were similar. The following account relies on detailed mapping made by both teams, the two sections having weaknesses as well as strengths. The section along the NW coast of Spain is of exceptional quality because of the high relief, but presents a “rootless suture”. On the French side, adding to the relatively poor quality of most outcrops, one has to take into account that the South-Armorican shear zone cuts across significant portions of the nappe stack, and therefore displaces the suture zone.

The **Autochthon** and **Parautochthon** are made of a thick sequence of dominantly terrigenous sediments laid down in the continental platform of northern Gondwana, including a few key lithological markers, namely (i) shallow-water carbonates of proved or presumed Early Cambrian age, (ii) a huge amount of felsic volcanics (“Ollo de Sapo” in Spain, “porphyroïdes” in France), both dated at about 490-470 Ma and derived from partial melting of a source that includes a significant Cadomian component, (iii) Early Ordovician quartzites frequently referred to as the Armorican Quartzite, and (iv) black shales and cherts of Silurian age.

The **Lower Allochthon** includes a terrigenous sequence of latest Proterozoic age intruded by Cambrian and Early Ordovician plutons (500-470 Ma), displaying a wide range of chemistries, including metaluminous, calc-alkaline rocks largely predominating over peralkaline bodies. These are recognized from Portugal to the Massif Central. A coeval or younger set of mafic bodies (mainly doleritic dykes) cuts across the granitoids and their country rocks. A younger terrigenous sequence of early Paleozoic age intercalates igneous mafic rocks both in France (Groix: 490-480 Ma, Bois de Cené: 490 Ma) and Spain (Ceán, Lamas de Abad, and Cercio units). This series represents the farther sections of a continent facing the Cambro-Ordovician Ocean that was involved in accretionary prisms at the onset of the Variscan cycle.

The **Middle Allochthon** consists of dismembered ophiolitic slices that locally display a blueschist-to eclogite-facies overprint during the Variscan orogeny. These include in NW Portugal and Spain a diverse array of well-characterized oceanic complexes, in many cases of Devonian age (Careón and Morais-Talhinhas: 400-395 Ma, Drain: 380 Ma). Other record Late Cambrian, Early Ordovician and younger Palaeozoic ages. Some are true ophiolitic bodies (Audierne: 480 Ma, Izeda-Remondes in Morais: ca. 450 Ma), others are better interpreted as accretionary prisms derived from an Early Ordovician ocean (Groix: 490-480 Ma, Bois de Cené: 490 Ma), or display a transitional ocean-continent domain (Vila de Cruces: 500Ma) related to the upper sequence of the Lower Allochthon.

The **Upper Allochthon** derives from a Late Cambrian, continental (ensialic) arc developed at the northern margin of Gondwana, and comprises two groups of units. Occupying the lower structural position, the first group preserves evidence of a high-pressure, granulite to eclogite-facies event (Bragança; Fornás, Belmil, Melide, and Sobrado in Órdenes; Cedeira, and A Capelada in Cabo Ortegal; upper slice of the Essarts Complex in Vendée). The eclogitic event was followed by partial melting and exhumation to amphibolite-facies conditions in the interval of 410-380 Ma. The upper group displays granulite (Monte Castelo and Corredoiras in Órdenes), amphibolite or greenschist facies metamorphism of Late Cambrian age, which closely followed arc formation. Amongst the low-grade units, that of Mauges in the SW Armorican Massif is unique because it preserves Cambrian or Early Ordovician sediments unconformably overlying a low-grade basement, followed by a discontinuous sedimentation recording the Hirnantian glaciation, then the Silurian anoxic event, and finally, the establishment of a carbonate platform close to an emerged land during the Early Devonian.

Geological map of the Iberian and Armorican Massifs, showing tectonic zones, magmatism, and sedimentation. The map includes a legend for post-Variscan cover, Variscan magmatism, and synorogenic sediments. It also features a detailed legend for allochthonous units and their geological ages, from Paleozoic cover to Late Ediacaran.